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PARATUS Serious Games evaluation survey

Section 1: General Information

Your age group (select one):

- 18–24
- 25–34
- 35–44
- 45–54
- 55–64
- 65+

Gender (select one):

- Female
- Male
- Prefer not to say
- Other: _____

What is your area of work? (select all that apply):

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Research | <input type="checkbox"/> Civil Protection / Emergency Services |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Government | <input type="checkbox"/> NGO / Civil Society |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Local Authority / Public Administration | <input type="checkbox"/> Education |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Private Sector | <input type="checkbox"/> Student |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> Other: _____ |

How satisfied are you with the overall workshop experience?

(1 = Very Dissatisfied, 5 = Very Satisfied)

1 2 3 4 5

How relevant did you find the content of the workshop to your role in disaster response/management?

(1 = Not Relevant, 5 = Very Relevant)

1 2 3 4 5

Do you think it is relevant to other people? If yes, to whom?

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Section 2: Learning Outcomes

How has the workshop affected your ability to make decisions under uncertain conditions?

(1 = Not at all, 5 = Significantly)

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1 2 3 4 5

To what extent did the simulation help you explore crisis scenarios?

(1 = Not at all, 5 = Significantly)

1 2 3 4 5

Did the workshop help you understand the experiences, perspectives, and complexity of vulnerable areas during a crisis?

(1 = Not at all, 5 = Significantly)

1 2 3 4 5

Have you learned something from this experience? What?

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What will stay with you after leaving the workshop room?

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Section 3: Simulation Design

Did any section of the support materials cause you to feel lost or confused?

- Yes
- No

If yes, what sections? How would you suggest improving it?

Which of the following was most helpful in gathering data necessary to make informed decisions in the simulation?

(Select one or more):

- Updates
- Maps
- Video
- None, I couldn't gather data
- Other: _____

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Section 4: Software Design

Was it easy for you to use the simulation software?

(1 = Not at all, 5 = Very easy)

1 2 3 4 5

If it was difficult, could you tell us why?

Section 5: Summary

How likely are you to apply the skills and knowledge gained from this workshop in your real-world professional context?

(1 = Unlikely, 5 = Very likely)

1 2 3 4 5

What was the most valuable aspect of the workshop for you?

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Do you have any additional comments or feedback regarding the workshop or suggestions for change?

Section 6: Thank You & Additional Information

Thank you!

Thank you for participating in the workshop with the PARATUS serious game(s) and taking the time to fill out the survey—your cooperation is greatly appreciated!

Additional Information

The serious game was created as part of the “PARATUS – Promoting disaster preparedness and resilience by co-developing stakeholder support tools for managing the systemic risk of compounding disasters” project, funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2021 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101073954.

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